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INDEX

Sl.No.	Topic	Page
1.	Geographical Interpretation of Physical Violence Against Women A Case Study of Bijnor Dr. Nirankar Singh Tyagi & Neeru Panwar	1-8
2.	Analytical Study of Emotional-Intelligence of Secondary School Teachers Jitendra Kumar & Prof. R.K. Srivastava	9-13
3.	Environmentally educated teachers-The priority of priorities? Dr. Shashi Singh & Dr. Chandra Dey	14-21
4.	Problems of Teaching English In India 22-25 Dr. Uday Singh	
5.	A Study of effect of Self-esteem's Education on Aggression in Adolescent Students Sundeep Kumar & Dr. M.K. Bhardwaj	26-29
6.	Effect of Computer Based Instruction on Academic Achievement In Social Science of IX Grade Students-an Experimental Study Suruchi Bansal & Dr. Neeru Mohini Agarwal	30-34
7.	Changing Context of Teacher Education in The Indian Scenario Dr. Rajkumari Singh & Dr. Manju Johari	35-38
8.	ROLE - Playing As A Method Of In Service Education Dr. Manoj Arya	39-41
9.	Teacher Education Facing Role Conflict In Ict Enabled Environment Dr. Pratibha Sagar & Dr. Deepti Johri	42-46
10.	THE RIGHT TO WORK (A STEP TO REALISE THE CONSTITUTIONAL GOAL) J.S. Bisht	47-50
11.	Child Labour : Stigma On Mankind Dr. Aryendu Dwivedi	51-54
12.	मोहनदास नैमिषराय की आत्मकथा में दलित जीवन की महत्वाकांक्षा सच्चाई, बेबसी की पीड़ा और मार्मिक संघर्षों का यथार्थ वर्णन श्रीमती प्रीति आर्य	55-58
13.	कृषि विकास एवं पर्यावरण अपघटन कुलवन्त सिंह	59-63

TEACHER EDUCATION FACING ROLE CONFLICT IN ICT ENABLED ENVIRONMENT

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Teaching is essential to the learning process. The emphasis of the teaching process has been centred around the teacher rather than the learner (Gagne, 1968). In recent history, the tendency has been to view the teacher as an impersonal "expert" in the classroom whose only role is to transmit knowledge, facts, skills to the "empty" learner. This paper attempts to challenge such limited conceptions of teaching and teachers by raising three basic questions:

- (1) what is the role of the teacher?
- (2) who is the teacher?
- (3) where does learning take place?

What is role of the teacher?

Teacher is considered to be the architect of the nation. In other words, the future of the nation lies in the hands of teacher. This shows the importance of teacher. According to Venna (2010), a teacher plays a significant role not only in class teaching learning situation but in social engineering too. Society gives a respectable place to teachers who are really empowered in terms of academic, intellectual, social, and national perspectives.

The teacher is someone who intervenes in the learning process of others. The process can be seen as providing prompts for engaging, stimulating, structuring, and encouraging learning in individuals and communities. While transmission of some types of knowledge and skills is part of this process and will continue to be important, the complexity of society and demands made on the problem-solving capacity of human beings will require that teaching be seen as fundamentally going beyond the transmission of information. In the world of the future, we envision that the teacher will be responsible for carrying out several inter-connected roles, as briefly described below.

Facilitator

During the last three decades, the changes in educational environment have been phenomenal. The role of the learner and technology has been changed drastically from traditional instruction to virtual learning environment. This new environment also involves a change in roles of both teachers and learners. The role of the teachers will change from knowledge transmitter to that of facilitator, knowledge navigator and sometime as co-learner. The new role of teachers demands a new way of thinking and understanding of the new vision of learning process (Resta, 2002). Facilitating learning entails building, accessing and validating a variety of activities, frameworks, information, and experiences for the learner to connect to. It should be clarified that facilitation implies more than simply providing access to new information or technologies; rather, it involves enabling understanding and creating meaning. This means raising the capacity of learners to ask questions rather than focusing on the provision of answers to predetermined questions.

Curriculum Innovation

Curricula around the world have often been unable to take into account the rich diversity in society and suffered from lack of imagination, flexibility and relevance. The result is that many learners find themselves "lost" in the learning process. Given the broad range of learning styles, needs, interests, backgrounds, and aspirations of learners, teachers must adapt and develop new curricular approaches, content and language to ensure that curricula are, on one level, linked to the daily life of the learner but, on another level, push the learners to explore beyond the mundane aspects of their daily lives into undiscovered possibilities. The movement towards decentralization provides an opportunity for allowing teachers greater control over the curricula.

Connection of Learners and Communities

While learning is an individualized effort, it is also a social activity. Teaching must be conceived of in terms of a larger social exercise of connecting learners to each other and to the world around them. The process of connecting learners involves creating dialogue among diverse groups of learners that allow them to understand and appreciate the differences as well as the similarities that bond us as human beings. This means that teachers must be committed to understanding their learners and the communities that they come from.

Complementing/Supplementing Other Channels

In addition to the traditional teacher, many other additional "channels" currently exist and are emerging, such as textbooks, newspapers, and magazines, educational radio or TV broadcasts, computers, audio or video tapes, the surrounding physical and human environment, libraries, specialized work areas such as to perform science experiments or for creative expression (Ahmed & Singh, 2010). Teaching becomes a process of integrating these resources so that they complement, supplement and enhance each other. This demands a sensitivity to the inherent strengths and weaknesses of each of the channels and how they satisfy to different styles of learning and different types of content. Teachers can also play a role in introducing these new media into communities where there is often fear or resistance to change.

Motivational Support

The teacher must play a critical role in providing motivational support through constructive feedback and encouragement to the learner, responding to a broad range of motivational needs that vary over time and across learners. Learning is a process that is filled with success and failure. It is the role of the teacher to provide positive inspiration at critical junctures of the learning process to ensure that learners stick with the laborious task of learning.

Learning

A good teacher is a continual learner. It's time for teachers, irrespective of who they teach, to realise that they will always be learners in Information and Communication Technology (ICT)-enabled environments and to become more aware of factors that enable their ongoing learning in such environments. It is now a curricula requirement that ICT is integrated into learning (ACARA, 2012a). In order to be effective, the teacher must remain connected with changing societal frames of reference (economic, cultural, political, social, technological, etc.) as well as with changing needs and interests of learners.

They must be able to learn from their environment. But more importantly, they must be able to learn from their learners. This involves constantly trying to understand how learners react to, interpret and create meaning from different activities. It also involves a willingness to experiment with and adapt new approaches. If the teacher demonstrates a dedication to learning, there is a high probability that the learners will "catch" that spirit of learning.

Who is a "teacher"?

The teacher in the institution has an important role to play in supporting the learning process. In order for continuous learning to occur, the responsibility for teaching must be distributed and integrated with other institutions and individuals in throughout society (Barr, 1958). We thus posit two broad categories of "teachers":

1) Human beings

This category includes the teacher in the classroom. But it also includes a wider range of individuals in society who are informally called upon to play equally important roles in complementing/supplementing the classroom teacher. These "teachers" build alternative learning environments and mediate access to diverse and valuable bodies of knowledge, traditions, information, skills, experiences, etc.

2) Media

The "teacher" should also be seen as including a variety of media for the learner to connect to. Such media-constructed environments include those that are built around technology and take the form of print, television, radio, computers, etc. The human "teacher" will be a medium among the other media, particularly in the sense that only the human teacher is capable of engaging in learning him or herself.

Where does learning take place?

Learning is a natural human process that occurs wherever human beings interact with each other and with their environments. Learning can take place in formal as well as informal settings. It is not uncommon that some of the best instances of learning occur outside a formal setting as the learners tend to be more at ease and learning tends to be more contextualized within a relevant socio-cultural setting. For learning both within and outside the formal context to become optimally effective, it is thus important that artificial barriers between the two environments be reduced. Different media can play an important role in bridging the gap.

Points of intervention in teacher education in ICT Enabled environments

Teacher education is an integrated part of a broader conception encompassing the education of both learners and teachers for their new roles in changing world, there is increased frustration with the existing process of teacher education when ICT is viewed as replacing the human element in teacher education (Drent & Meelissen, 2008). Many attempt at improving the quality and motivation of "teachers/learners" through teacher training schemes have resulted in disappointment. The use of ICT is often advocated to overcome such weaknesses and if ICT's are properly applied it possess the ability to unleash revolutionary changes in the field of teacher education. Some focal points for application of ICT into teacher education have been suggested:

Participatory teacher education

Teacher education should be geared towards building a link between the various "teacher/learners" in society. Selected joint training sessions may be organized to do this with ICTs being utilized to facilitate greater communication, collaboration and reflection among the various partners. Initial sessions

could start with discussions on how to work together, sharing of roles, and ensuring overlap (for reinforced learning).

Flexible training for specific needs of teachers

One of the strengths of the ICTs is that they facilitate moving away from generic teacher education models with relatively little relevance to the lives and daily problems of the "teacher/learner." The ICTs allow for the development of specific training models that are sensitive to the different needs, working conditions, learning styles, language and backgrounds of individual "teacher/learners."

Teacher education conceived of as on-going and in the learning environment

The ICTs allow the potential for teacher education to be moved out of centralized training institutions and into the "teacher/learner's" own working environment. In addition, they open up the opportunity to think of teacher education as a career-long career-wide activity. Such an emphasis on on-going training is essential to allowing the "teacher/learners" to continually reflect on critical aspects of their own teaching as well as critical aspects of their own learning.

Overcoming the dichotomy between subject matter and pedagogy

The ICTs allow us to rethink the content of teacher education. Traditionally there has been an artificial dichotomy between mastery of subject matter and pedagogical skills, sometimes with a tendency for teacher education to emphasize the subject matter aspect of the content. Teacher education content should be re-oriented to focus on learning and learners with subject matter and pedagogical elements integrated around this focus. In addition, the ICTs should be used to make teacher education more consistent with the pedagogical concerns being advocated, such as active learning, critical thinking, collaborative processes and creativity.

Interacting with different media

Noting the expanding role the new media are already playing in the provision of education and cognizant of how this role will undoubtedly expand, it is critical to recognize the importance of media literacy among "teacher/learners." Such media literacy requires a strong understanding of the strengths and limitations of each medium and familiarity with strategies to reinforce the effect one medium can have on learning through the use of other media. Teacher education should ensure that teachers interact and experiment with these various media and creatively reflect upon how they can best be used in different learning environments. This should be more than a mere theoretical exercise and actually involve hands-on experience.

Conclusions

Technology has posed an opportunity to create processes that encourage teachers to become learners and learners to become teachers. This is a major shift in role change. The question that remains is how to facilitate this shift. However, two powerful tools are available to us i.e. first and foremost is our capacity to learn and second is the power of ICTs themselves to enhance such learning. ICT advantage can be taken in building environment for such roles and relationships which further calls for a commitment to view ourselves not only as experts but also as learners, the starting point for effective change in role thus lies in our willingness to change ourselves.

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आवश्यक निर्देश

इस शोध पत्रिका का प्रकाशन अर्द्धवार्षिक रूप में फरवरी एवं अगस्त माह में हो रहा है। प्रकाशनार्थ शोध लेख भेजने से पूर्व कृपया निम्न निर्देशों के पालन की अपेक्षा की जाती है-

लेख अंग्रेजी में MS World Set up में Times New Roman Font एवं हिन्दी में Krutidev 010 में मूल कॉपी/सी०डी० में प्रेषित करें या फिर आप अपने लेख dr_dkverma74@yahoo.com ईमेल आई०डी० पर भी भेज सकते हैं।

शोध लेख स्तरीय एवं मौलिक होने पर ही प्रकाशनार्थ स्वीकार किया जायेगा। आप अपने शोध लेख की प्रति सुरक्षित रखें ताकि अस्वीकृत होने की स्थिति में शोध लेख की चापसी सम्भव नहीं होगी। मौलिकता के साक्ष्य के रूप में लेखक को प्रमाण-पत्र देना होगा। लेख के अन्त में संदर्भों को वर्णमाला के अक्षरों के क्रम (Alphabetically) में ही प्रेषित करें।

शोध पत्र सामान्यतया 2500 शब्दों से अधिक नहीं होना चाहिए। इसके साथ ही संक्षिप्त सारांश लगभग 200-300 शब्दों तक भेजा जाये।

पुस्तक की समीक्षा हेतु लेखक/प्रकाशक को पुस्तक की दो प्रतियां प्रधान सम्पादक को प्रेषित करनी चाहिए।

शोध लेख भेजने के बाद प्रकाशन की गारण्टी नहीं दी जा सकती। स्वीकृत-अस्वीकृत करने का पूरा अधिकार प्रधान सम्पादक को ही है। लेख प्रकाशित होने पर लेखक को शोध पत्रिका की प्रति उनके पते पर डाक द्वारा प्रेषित कर दी जायेगी। पत्रिका का शुल्क निम्नलिखित पते पर मनीआर्डर द्वारा भेजे।

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डा० धर्मेन्द्र कुमार

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